

STUDY OF EDUCATIONAL TERMINOLOGY IN UZBEK LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: In today's article, opinions are expressed about the widespread promotion of Uzbek and English linguistics, the use of words, the origin of terms, and the importance of terminology.

Key words: term, Uzbek and English linguistics, opinion, mass information, understanding, learning

At present, Uzbek terminology is developing rapidly in all directions. The basic concepts of science, science and technology, politics, economy and cultural life are provided with a proportional terminology system. During the years of independence, various bilingual, multilingual and explanatory dictionaries appeared in the country. At the moment, intensive work is being done on the creation of terminological dictionaries for various fields, and educational, methodological and scientific literature on terminology is being published. Mass media plays an important role in the further development of Uzbek terminology. It is a fact that the main source of the enrichment, completion and improvement of the specific terminological system of the modern Uzbek literary language, as it happens in other languages, is undoubtedly its own vocabulary. The development of Uzbek terminology at the expense of its own resources and opportunities occurs in two ways: a) the use of ready-made words in the language to express new things-subjects and concepts: b) the possibilities of the Uzbek literary language to create words the creation of new terms with participation. When creating new terms, morphological, semantic and syntactic methods of word formation are effectively used. The shielding method also plays a significant role in the creation

of terms. A huge share of the terminology of the Uzbek language is made up of names that have appeared on the basis of the Russian-international fund. The terms borrowed from other non-Turkic languages are characterized by the fact that the Uzbek people cover the social, political, economic, social, cultural, and spiritual aspects of the activity. The adoption of the Law "On the State Language" by the Supreme Council of Uzbekistan on October 21, 1989, required a new approach to the terminological lexicon, which is considered one of the main layers of the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. As stated in Article 7 of the law, "The state ensures the enrichment and improvement of the Uzbek language, including the introduction of universally recognized scientific-technical and socio-political terms." After the adoption of this universally important Law, the tendency to revise the terms that were already in use in the language, especially the Russian-international layer, increased for about 3-5 years. Undoubtedly, such efforts gained importance as they aimed to preserve the purity of the Uzbek language and restore its original nature.

Since there is no alternative to certain concepts in the terminology system of the Uzbek language, the possibility of expressing them with one word is limited. Explaining or describing a foreign concept using a number of words is contrary to the requirements of terminology. We observe the same situation in the system of linguistic terms: accent, articulation, phonetics, phoneme, diphthong, reduction, metathesis, dissimilation, logography, affix, pragmatics, syntagmatic, semantics, idiom, infinitive, gerund, semiotics, synergetics, metalinguistics, morphology, concept, gestalt, biolinguistics, discourse. The rapid development of science, technology and production, processes of globalization and integration taking place in the developed countries of the world, and the entry of languages into mutual relations created the basis for the enrichment of their lexical fund. For example, it is impossible to imagine today's life without modern information and communication networks, in particular, the Internet and the system of terms used in this field. Internet terms that are part of the terminology of the Uzbek language

mainly consist of borrowings, which were borrowed from two languages, namely English. We note that it is possible to recommend using the lexemes of anchor instead of anchor, dam instead of gateway, letter instead of font, and branch instead of the highway. In the current state of terminology of the Uzbek language, we can witness the simultaneous use of own and borrowed words. This process testifies to the conflict between the norm of the previous terminological system and the new lexical unit, "struggle for survival". Linguistic life, speech practice and time will show which of the natural, competing terms will occupy a worthy place in the terminology of the Uzbek language. In some situations, if any concept is expressed by two terms, i.e. native and foreign (English-international), the Uzbek term is undoubtedly preferred.

The Uzbek language is one of the languages rich in words. We can include both formal and informal conversations as examples. Many of the words we use have come from the languages of other countries and nations. That is why terminology is very important to us in order to clearly understand the words in the pure Uzbek language. Terminology clearly shows how words are used, where they come from, and what meanings they are used.

Uzbek terminologists have the responsibility to solve the underlying problems as well as the problems mentioned above: the lack of proportional versions of some terms of a general nature; unsatisfactory regulation and unification of science and technology field terms; allowing spelling confusion in the use of terms; lack of approach to terminology issues based on today's requirements, management and control of the process of creating and publishing various terminological dictionaries; absence of a methodical manual and periodical bulletin that ensures the accuracy of the terms used in various fields; terminological lexicon, especially the lack of satisfactory theoretical research on the scientific and technical terms of the Independence period; absence of a management and monitoring body that deals specifically with issues of terminology. Uzbek terminological dictionaries, so to speak, cover almost all fields

of science. The dictionary (terminography) works aimed at expressing the meaning of the terms used in the fields of social and humanitarian sciences, such as specific sciences, were compiled by leading scientists of the republic's research institutes, professors and teachers of higher educational institutions. Most of the terminological dictionaries are devoted to the issue of the expression of terms borrowed from the Russian language in Uzbek.

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